

LIBRARY AS A LEARNING HUB: ASSESSING USER SATISFACTION IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has transformed the entire landscape of academic libraries, shifting them from traditional formats to digital libraries. Libraries play a crucial role in academic institutions by providing information resources and services to both students and teachers. In India, the digital education system is transforming traditional classrooms into digital ones to enhance learning skills, improve student evaluation systems, provide quality content for faster and more effective learning. The main aim of this study is to understand students' satisfaction with library resources. Data was collected from both primary and secondary sources. The primary data was collected through a google forms questionnaire from 223 respondents using a convenient sampling method.

Keywords: Library, Students, Satisfaction, Library users and Education.

INTRODUCTION

Libraries are established as service-oriented institutions in society, providing a variety of informative resources and services. In the 21st century, classrooms are equipped with smart boards instead of traditional chalkboards, and both teachers and students increasingly prefer virtual modes of learning over physical ones. Modern learning methods are designed with integrated technology that enables students to achieve specific goals and objectives. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has transformed the entire landscape of academic libraries, shifting them from traditional formats to digital libraries. Digitization and technological advancements are influencing all aspects of the education system. Until recently, traditional learning methods prevailed, where teachers lectured, and students passively listened, often without the opportunity for active participation. Advanced technology has revolutionized this process, enabling both students and teachers to adapt to the evolving educational environment. Digital libraries are much more than repositories of books; they are dynamic centers of learning, designed to help students and teachers optimize their use of information resources. Specifically established to benefit both educators and learners, academic libraries remain integral components of educational institutions.

Digital libraries offer a wide range of information services, encompassing both traditional print materials and digital resources. Library staff play a critical role in ensuring student satisfaction. They must regularly assess library resources and actively seek feedback from both teachers and students to continuously enhance and improve overall library services.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Fasa Rachael Aladeniyi and Temitope Samuel Owokole (2018) clearly presented the use of library resources. The authors found that students acknowledged the availability of all the resources listed in the questionnaire and that most students used the library for general information, examinations, assignments, and research purposes. The study revealed that the majority of respondents used library resources occasionally, with textbooks being the most frequently utilized resource. Only a few respondents reported experiencing challenges in using the library resources. The authors suggested measures to promote better use of the library's information resources at the University of Medical Science, Ondo State, Nigeria. The study concluded that there is a need to encourage students to utilize library resources more effectively.

Prema Jayaraj & Kannappanavar B. U. (2021) presented the awareness and utilization of library resources by faculty

members and students. The author found that sample respondents opened that education institutions need to provide more computers with internet facilities. The author suggested that libraries need to focus on student orientation programmes need to promote the use of library resources and services. The study concluded that library professionals encourage the faculty members and students to use resources available in library for their teaching and learning purposes.

Onwubiko Emmanuel Chidiadi (2022) analyzed the level of awareness, utilization of e-resources and challenges faced in utilization of e-resources. The author suggested that provide up-to-date information that will enhance research and innovation. The study concluded that use of search engines usually requires less effort to retrieve information but the implication is that it increases the rate of plagiarism among students and it leads to low quality research work.

Kokkula Surendher (2022) discussed the impact of information communication technology (ICT) on libraries and ICT based services. The author found that govt. of India also launched support programs to improve the quality of higher education. The author suggested that ICTs need to transformed libraries and their services to reach remote uses and improved access to information for their users with various digital platforms. The study concluded that e-library services has improved the teaching and learning.

Banda Boniface (2023) this study analyzes the challenges of students in accessing library services. The author found that most of the students were not aware of the services available in the library. The study concluded that create more awareness, student education on information literacy of library resources, encouraging the use of social media platforms, training and initiation of borrowing of library resources to library management.

Zihadur Rahman, Nur Ahammad, Samira Islam and Md Armanul Haque (2025) explained the user satisfaction with library services, focused on how staff behavior mediates the relationship between library services, resources and overall user satisfaction. The author found that majority users opened that satisfied with the library physical collections, library catalog, staff services. The author suggested that need to enhance library academic and research collections, upgrade internet speed with Wi-Fi access, increase seating and printing facilities.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To understand the students' satisfaction with the library resources.

METHODOLOGY

The main objective of the study is to understand the students' level of satisfaction with library resources. The primary data was gathered through a Google Forms questionnaire administered to 223 respondents using a convenient sampling method. Secondary data was obtained from publications and websites. The sample for this study includes intermediate and graduate students, who were selected based on convenient sampling.

PROFILE OF THE STUDENTS

The socio-economic profile of the students taken from both rural and urban areas. The sample respondents profile i.e., location, gender and age analyzed based on the primary data. The socio-economic profile of the students shown in the following tables.

Table - 1

Area of the Sample Students

Area of the Sample Students	No. of the Sample Respondents	In %
Rural	128	57.4
Urban	95	42.6
Total	223	100

Source: Primary data.

Table - 2

Gender of the Sample Students

Gender of the Sample Students	No. of the Sample Respondents	In %
Male	147	65.9
Female	76	34.1
Total	223	100

Source: Primary data.

Table - 3

Age of the Sample Students

Age of the Sample Students	No. of the Sample Respondents	In %
10 to 20 Years	136	61
20 to 30 Years	87	39
Total	223	100

Source: Primary data.

The overall analysis inferred from the above tables indicates

that the majority of the sample respondents are living in urban areas, while the remaining respondents are from rural areas. The results also show that 62 percent of the respondents are male and 38 percent are female in the study area. Table-4 presents the satisfaction levels of library users with the current library opening hours.

Table - 4

Satisfaction of Library Users with the current library opening hours

Satisfaction of Library Users with the current library opening hours	No. of the Sample Respondents	In %
Yes, fully satisfied	119	53.4
Satisfied to some extent	96	43
Not satisfied	08	3.6
Total	223	100

Source: Primary data.

It is observed from table 4 that 53.4 percent of the students are satisfied with the current library opening hours, while some students are only partially satisfied. A few students expressed dissatisfaction with the library services. Table-5 presents the opinions of library users regarding the availability of required textbooks and reference books.

Table - 5

Library Users Rating on the availability of required textbooks/reference books

Library Users Rating on the availability of required textbooks/reference books	No. of the Sample Respondents	In %
Always available	112	50.2
Available most of the time	94	42.2
Rarely available	17	7.6
Total	223	100

Source: Primary data.

Table 5 presents the opinions of library users on the availability of required textbooks and reference books. It shows that the majority of the sample students reported that the required textbooks and reference books are always available in their libraries, while only a few students indicated that these resources are rarely available. Table-6 presents the opinions of library users on digital resources.

Table-6

Library Users opinion on digital resources (e-books, e-journals, databases)

Library Users opinion on digital resources	No. of the Sample Respondents	In %
Very useful	67	30

Useful	142	63.7
Less useful	14	6.3
Total	223	100

Source: Primary data.

Table 6 shows, most of the students stated that the library digital resources are very useful for their studies, while only a few students felt that the digital resources are less useful for their academics. Table-7 presents the library users' opinions on the seating and study facilities in the library.

Table - 7

Library Users opinion on Seating and study facilities in the library

Library Users opinion on Seating and study facilities in the library	No. of the Sample Respondents	In %
Excellent	58	26
Good	150	67.3
Average	14	6.3
Poor	01	0.4
Total	223	100

Source: Primary data.

Table 7 illustrates the library users' opinions on seating and study facilities in the library. The overall analysis indicates that the majority of respondents reported being satisfied with the seating and study facilities. Some of the students stated that they were moderately satisfied with these facilities. The library users' opinions on the helpfulness of library staff are presented in Table-8.

Table - 8

Library Users opinion on helpfulness of library staff

Library Users opinion on helpfulness of library staff	No. of the Sample Respondents	In %
Very helpful	57	25.6
Helpful	155	69.5
Less helpful	11	4.9
Total	223	100

Source: Primary data.

Further, Table 8 presents the library users' opinions on the helpfulness of the library staff. It shows that the majority of the sample students stated that they are satisfied with the services provided by the library staff. Only a few students stated that they are dissatisfied with the services provided by the library staff. Table-9 shows the library users' opinions on the guidance provided for accessing resources.

Table - 9

Library Users opinion on guidance provided for accessing resources

(Catalog, databases, e-resources)

Library Users opinion on guidance provided for accessing resources	No. of the Sample Respondents	In %
Very satisfied	41	18.4
Satisfied	176	78.9
Dissatisfied	04	1.8
Very dissatisfied	02	0.9
Total	223	100

Source: Primary data.

Table 9 explains the library users' opinions on the guidance provided for accessing resources. It shows that the majority of the sample students stated that they were satisfied with the guidance provided for accessing resources such as the catalog, databases, and e-resources. Only a few students stated that they were dissatisfied with the guidance provided for accessing these resources.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- It is observed from the analysis that 53.4 percent of the sample students are satisfied with the library opening hours, while some students are only partially satisfied. A few students reported being dissatisfied with the library services.
- The majority of the sample students stated that required textbooks and reference books are always available in the library, while a smaller portion mentioned that such materials are rarely available.
- Most students indicated that the library's digital resources are very useful for their studies, whereas only a few felt that these resources are less useful for their academics.
- The overall analysis shows that most of the sample respondents are satisfied with the seating and study facilities in the library, while some expressed moderate satisfaction.
- Most of the students satisfied with the services provided by the library staff, with only a few expressing dissatisfactions.
- Among total sample respondents most of the students stated that they are satisfied with the guidance provided for accessing resources (such as catalogues, databases, and e-resources), while a small number of students reported dissatisfaction in this regard.

SUGGESTIONS

- Libraries need to acquire the latest edition of books in accordance with the university syllabus and provide materials related to competitive exams for students.
- The library should revise and update its collection development policy to address the needs of all users, including students, research scholars, and faculty members.
- College management should allocate an adequate budget for the purchase of various library resources. Teaching staff should enhance students' awareness of the available resources in the college library.
- College authorities should make library orientation sessions mandatory for all newly enrolled students and provide regular exercises to ensure the effective utilization of resources.

CONCLUSION

Educational institution libraries play a crucial role in enhancing the academic and research abilities of students and scholars. Although information is widely available on digital platforms, most students still prefer printed learning materials. Advances in the internet and technology have enabled academic libraries to offer multi-disciplinary and innovative library services. The study concludes that academic institutions should integrate the use of library resources into their curriculum, as this will help students gain more knowledge and significantly support academic activities within the institution.

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